

Cultural heritage and tourism. A comparison of two destinations in Southern Moravia

Tourism and Hospitality Research
2022, Vol. 0(0) 1–12

© The Author(s) 2022

Article reuse guidelines:

sagepub.com/journals-permissions

DOI: 10.1177/14673584221089747

journals.sagepub.com/home/thr

Milada Štastná* and **Antonín Vaishar**

Department of Applied and Landscape Ecology, Mendel University in Brno, Brno, Czech Republic

Abstract

This paper addresses the question: why do two destinations with extremely valuable cultural heritage gain attractions have completely different tourism traffic results? The main aim of this paper was to find the various causes of this inequality. The comparative method was used and Lednice and Dolní Kounice in Southern Moravia were selected as case studies. Statistical data and strategic documents on regional and local levels were analysed. The study showed significant differences in the strategic conceptual plans. Dolní Kounice was a more popular destination for suburban tourism for the inhabitants of Brno, the historical heritage was only an added value. In the case of Lednice, the use of its heritage for tourism was one of the main development priorities. This paper further noted that cultural tourism is often seen as a sector of the economy rather than a part of the culture.